

Onboarding Guidelines for the EOSC Finland Pilot Node, 1.0

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Finland

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1. Introduction to the Onboarding Guidelines

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) program aims to create an open, shared digital research environment for Europe. It promotes research and innovation by making it easier to discover and use research datasets, services, and tools in line with FAIR principles and the guidelines of open science and research. All content types, including services, are collectively referred to as resources. The research environment consists of research infrastructures, national and international networks and their nodes, which together form the EOSC Federation.

The [EOSC Finland Pilot Node](#) offers service providers and researchers visibility and access to digital resources on national and EOSC Federation levels. By publishing metadata about services or data in the EOSC Finland Pilot Node, service providers can make their services and other resources widely accessible and findable for researchers. The formation of Finland's pilot node is facilitated by CSC – IT Center for Science, which maintains core capabilities and the resources of Finland's pilot node on behalf of the Ministry of Education and Culture.

Figure 1. The interim governance model. Thematic working groups can report either to the Node Operations Committee or directly to the Node Coordination Committee. The latter consists of the Node Coordinators. The EOSC Association provides coordination and support for the Federation. The Nodes are responsible for their own costs and operations.

In March 2025, EOSC entered the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. During this build-up phase, thirteen candidate nodes were developed, aiming to technically interconnect and to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources. The EOSC Finland Pilot Node was one of

these candidate nodes and will serve as one of the entry points to the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services.

It will be possible to onboard services and data resources on both a national and an EOSC level. National level onboarding makes resources available for researchers with a Finnish affiliation (as a minimum), while EOSC level onboarding offers the resource to researchers in [Horizon Europe countries](#) with some additions.

In the EOSC Federation, the aim is to federate different types of research resources. In the EOSC Finland Pilot Node, these resources are primarily different types of data, e.g. use copies (Dataset-as-a-Service), research databases, or datasets. Also other resources, like virtual research environments and tools, have been identified and may be included later. Metadata about onboarded resources that are federated on EOSC level is conveyed from the EOSC Finland Pilot Node to the [EOSC EU Node](#) (EEN) and is made available via APIs. The ownership and responsibility of the onboarded resources remain with the onboarding party. The EOSC Finland Pilot Node adheres to the [CSC Data Policy](#), [CSC Data Management Policy](#), and the core services to [CSC Terms of Use](#) for services for research, including the requirements for [free-of-charge use](#). Onboarding resources to the EOSC Finland Pilot Node is free and does not require membership in the EOSC Association. However, onboarding should comply with the criteria described in this documentation and it is recommended that onboarding parties/organisations [join as a member](#) of the EOSC Finnish Forum and participate in its activities.

The EOSC Federation is planned to go into production in the autumn of 2026.

2. The EOSC Federation and the EOSC Finland Pilot Node

The legal framework of the EOSC Federation and its organisation is under negotiation. EOSC is considered relevant for supporting European research and innovation, and eventually European digital sovereignty.

The EOSC Federation is currently based on a [Memorandum of Understanding](#) signed by the nodes. The current governance structures are described in this document.

Figure 2. Interim policy governance model for piloting phase in Finland.

The requirements for federation on an EOSC level and to the [EOSC EU reference Node \(EEN\)](#) are described in the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#).

EOSC Finland Pilot Node resources

- Core capabilities
 - AAI
 - Search
 - Helpdesk
 - Monitoring
- Node resources
 - Research services offered by the Ministry of Education and Culture
- Node Exchange
 - Resources federated on EOSC level

Figure 3. CSC provides the core capabilities for the EOSC Finland Pilot Node. Other service and resource providers can onboard their resources on a national level and also choose to join the Node Exchange, if they are eligible for EOSC level federation.

The EOSC Finland Pilot Node federates its core capabilities provided by CSC with the EEN and coordinates the Node Exchange, i.e. federated resources, through the EOSC Finland Pilot Node. The planning of the catalogue(s) is done within the National EOSC Policy Governance collaboration. Services, data sources, and research data sources may be onboarded in three ways: at a national level, at an EOSC level, or both. In the future, other types of resources may be added. A resource can be onboarded in several nodes, and as e.g. a service and a data source.

3. How you can federate

3.1 National federation

1. The resource is made discoverable through national services, i.e. Fairdata Etsin and/or the EOSC Finland Pilot Node Service catalogue. In the future other catalogues, e.g. for tools and applications, may be included.
2. The resource must adhere to FAIR principles and national reference architectures. The hosting organisation should commit to the [national Open Science Declaration](#).
3. Researchers can access and use the resource directly (open access) or by using the national Haka credentials. Implementing SSO should be preferred if possible. A service may require registration before use.

Criteria for national level onboarding

- A mature service or a managed resource is considered case by case during the piloting phase
- Available and useful for researchers or RDM professionals in Finland
- Supports the FAIR principles, e.g. adheres to national PID guidelines and strategies. Regarding data, read more on [Fairdata](#)
- Haka federated (Haka login) or fully open access

Service in EOSC Finland used for onboarding resources

Resource type	Service in the Finnish Node
Service	EOSC Finland Pilot Node Service Catalogue
Dataset	Fairdata Services
Dataset-as-a-Service data (use copy in e.g. Allas or LUMI)	Fairdata Services and relevant service in HPC environment
Research Data Source	Fairdata Services

3.2 EOSC level federation

This means joining the Node Exchange.

1. The resource is made accessible via [MyAccessID/EOSC AAI](#)
2. The resource is made discoverable via the [EEN and Node APIs resource hub](#) (e.g. “Tier 3”)

Criteria for Federation level onboarding

- A mature service or a managed resource is considered case by case during the piloting phase
- Available and useful for researchers or RDM professionals in Europe
- EOSC AAI federated (MyAccessID federation and login via the EOSC Finland Pilot Node)
- FAIR supporting
- Upcoming requirements on monitoring and helpdesk federations

4. Support provided by the EOSC Finland Pilot Node

CSC provides the following support for onboarding:

- support for AAI federation
- support in metadata creation and publication
- support in publishing metadata

Under development:

- All data models might be subject to changes
- Catalogues for tools and other types of resources
- MyAccessID/EOSC AAI federation for non-CSC services
- Help desk and monitoring federation is being planned

5. Onboarding and offboarding a resource

Onboarding

1. Get in touch with the EOSC Finland Pilot Node
2. Together validate metadata and ensure that the resource meets EOSC and Node requirements
3. Review of resource in collaboration with the [Open Science EOSC WG](#)

4. Agree on federation, i.e. providing metadata and access and provide contact information
5. Curate and manage resource, keep contact information and resource metadata up to date

Offboarding

6. If offboarding from the EOSC Finland Pilot Node, please get in touch in with the Node

6. Contact

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<https://research.csc.fi/support/>

7. Authors

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Links to relevant documents

- EOSC Federation Handbook 2.0 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454649>
- Dietrich, M., & Scardaci, D. (EOSC Future, 2024). Guidelines for Onboarding Resources to EOSC Exchange. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10621226>
- This document in Finnish: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20023634>

Appendix: EOSC FI English–Finnish glossary

Source: EOSC Federation Handbook v. 2.0, unless otherwise mentioned

EOSC Association

The EOSC Association is the legal entity established to govern the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It was formed on 29 July 2020 with four founding members, and has since grown to 250 Members and Observers. It is registered in Belgium.

N.B.: The EOSC Association is also known by abbreviations EOSC A and EOSC-A. At this stage, the official name of the EOSC Association will be used.

EOSC Association on yhdistys, joka on perustettu hallinnoimaan Euroopan avoimen tieteen pilvi (European Open Science Cloud, EOSC) -toimintaa. Se perustettiin 29. heinäkuuta 2020 neljän perustajajäsenen voimin ja on sittemmin kasvanut yli 250 jäsenen ja tarkkailijan verkostoksi. Yhdistys on rekisteröity Belgiaan.

Kommentti: EOSC Associationista käytetään myös lyhennettä EOSC A ja EOSC-A. Tässä vaiheessa käytämme EOSC Associationista sen virallista nimeä.

Source: eosc.eu

EOSC Federation – EOSC-federaatio

The network of EOSC Nodes, which collectively integrate their resources to provide shared system-level functions, known as Federating Capabilities. These capabilities – which include a common catalogue for resource discovery, a federated user login system (AAI), and coordinated monitoring – are the glue that ensures consistency and interoperability across the network.

N.B.: In this context, the Federation is a technical, stable, and decentralised collaboration model. It requires trust between the different actors, cf. Haka Federation.

EOSC-noodien verkosto, joka yhdistää resurssinsa tarjotakseen jaettuja järjestelmätason toimintoja, tunnettuina yhdistämiskyvykkyyksinä. Nämä kyvykkyydet varmistavat verkoston yhdenmukaisuuden ja yhteensopivuuden ja toimivat yhdysiteenä. Niihin kuuluvat yhteinen resurssien löytämiseen tarkoitettu luettelo, federoitu käyttäjätunnistusjärjestelmä (AAI) ja koordinoitu seuranta.

Kommentti: Tässä yhteydessä federaatio on tekninen, vakaa ja hajautettu yhteistoimintamalli. Edellyttää luottamusta toimijoiden välillä, vrt. Haka-federaatio.

EOSC Node – EOSC-noodi

An organisation complying with the EOSC Federation policies and legal framework, sharing resources at the local, national, regional, thematic or European level. An EOSC Node offers Resources which provide added value to the EOSC Federation and implements Federating Capabilities in collaboration with other EOSC Nodes. Each EOSC Node is responsible for its autonomy, governance and resources. It operates its own platform, complying with the EOSC Interoperability Framework and the EOSC Node architecture.

EOSC-noodi on toimija tai yhteisö, joka noudattaa EOSC-federaation politiikkoja ja oikeudellista viitekehystä ja jakaa resursseja paikallisella, kansallisella, alueellisella, teema-alueellisella tai

eurooppalaisella tasolla. EOSC-noodi tarjoaa resursseja, jotka tuottavat lisäarvoa EOSC-federaatiolle, ja toteuttaa yhdistämiskyvykkyudet yhteistyössä muiden EOSC-noodien kanssa. Jokainen EOSC-noodi vastaa omasta autonomiastaan, hallinnostaan ja resursseistaan. Se ylläpitää omaa alustaansa noudattaen EOSC Interoperability Framework -teknistä viitekehystä sekä EOSC-noodiarkkitehtuuria.

EOSC Node host – EOSC-noodin vastuutaho

The legal entity representing an EOSC Node, which signs the EOSC Memorandum of Understanding. For EOSC Finland, this organisation is CSC.

Vastuutaho, joka edustaa EOSC-noodia ja allekirjoittaa EOSC-aiesopimuksen. EOSC Finlandin osalta tämä organisaatio on CSC.

EOSC resource provider – EOSC-resurssin tarjoaja

An organisation making a Resource available through an EOSC Node to the EOSC Federation. The resource is then called an EOSC Federation Resource and it becomes part of the EOSC Node Exchange of the EOSC Node. In Finland the resource providers are organisations, not e.g. individual researchers.

Organisaatio, joka tarjoaa resursseja EOSC-federaatioon EOSC-noodin kautta. Resurssia kutsutaan tällöin EOSC-federaation resurssiksi ja siitä tulee osa EOSC-noodin tarjoamaa (Node Exchange). Suomessa resursseja voivat tarjota vain organisaatiot, ei esimerkiksi yksittäiset tutkijat.

Federating Capability – Yhdistämiskyvykkyys

System of services provided by more than one EOSC Node in order to implement the federation of resources in the EOSC Federation.

Palveluiden ja järjestelmien kokonaisuus, jonka avulla federaation resurssien yhdistäminen toteutetaan EOSC-federaatioissa.

Node Exchange – Noodin EOSC-tarjoama

Services and other resources a Node makes available to the EOSC Federation.

Palvelut ja muut resurssit, joita tarjotaan noodin kautta EOSC-federaatioon.

National service provider – Kansallisen tason palveluntarjoaja

See “onboarding – liittyminen” below.

Cf. the DAHA local level, national level, and international level services.

Ks. “onboarding – liittyminen” alempana.

Vrt. DAHA paikallisen tason, kansallisen tason ja kansainvälisen tason palvelut.

Node Core Capability – Noodin ydinkvykykkyys

The capabilities that enable the operation of a Node (e.g. AAI, Helpdesk, Monitoring).

Kyvykkyydet, jotka mahdollistavat EOSC-noodin toiminnan (esim. käyttäjätunnistus (AAI), tukipalvelu ja seuranta).

Onboarding – Liittyminen

Resources are onboarded in an EOSC Node when they are integrated into an EOSC Node. The provider selects the most appropriate node based on the characteristics of the resource. For example, if a provider has a domain-specific data repository, it may choose a thematic node that best represents and serves that domain. A resource can be onboarded to multiple nodes.

Resurssit liitetään EOSC-noodiin, kun ne integroidaan siihen. Resurssin tarjoaja valitsee sopivimman noodin resurssin ominaisuuksien perusteella. Jos tarjoajalla on esimerkiksi alan erityinen tietovarasto, se voi valita teemaan parhaiten sopivan EOSC-noodin, joka edustaa ja palvelee kyseistä aluetta. Resurssi voidaan liittää useaan noodiin.

Research resource – Tutkimusresurssi

Services, catalogues, digital research objects (e.g. data, software), training resources, infrastructure and other assets that may be available in an EOSC Node and offered in the EOSC Federation.

See also <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-167>

Palvelut, luettelot, digitaaliset tutkimusobjektit (esim. data, ohjelmistot), koulutusresurssit, infrastruktuuri ja muut varat, joita voi olla tarjolla EOSC-noodissa ja jotka tarjotaan EOSC-federaatiossa.

Ks. myös <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-167>

Research data source – Tutkimusdatalähde

Sources where data can be found and retrieved, offering APIs or direct access to data searches across various query fields. Data repositories and archives, knowledge bases and scientific databases fall into this category.

Lähteet, joista dataa voi hakea ja noutaa, ja jotka tarjoavat rajapintoja (API) tai suoraa pääsyä datan hakuun eri hakukenttien kautta. Tähän luokkaan kuuluvat tietovarastot ja -arkistot, tietokannat sekä tieteelliset tietokannat.

Research software – Tutkimusohjelmistot

Source code, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows, and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose.

N.B.: in DAHA, "source code: a programmatic description of the means by which data has been produced or processed."

Linked concept: <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-172>

Lähdekoodi, algoritmit, skriptit, laskennalliset työnkulut ja suoritettavat ohjelmat, jotka on luotu tutkimusprosessin aikana tai tutkimustarkoitukseen.

Kommentti: DAHA:ssa "lähdekoodi: ohjelmallinen kuvaus keinosta, jolla dataa on tuotettu tai käsitelty."

Liittyvä käsite: <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-172>

Research tools – Tutkimuksen työkalut

Analytical, visualisation and other types of tools to aid in the interpretation, transformation and presentation of data. Tools may include dashboards, plotting software, data anonymisation software and machine learning frameworks.

Analyttiset, visualisointi- ja muut työkalut, jotka tukevat datan tulkintaa, muokkausta ja esittämistä. Työkaluihin voivat kuulua hallintapaneelit, kuvaajien piirtämishjelmistot, datan anonymisointihjelmistot sekä koneoppimishjelmistokehykset.

Service – Palvelu

A productised package that delivers value to the customer and is ready for immediate use.

See also <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-18205>

Tuotteistettu kokonaisuus, jolla tuotetaan asiakkaalle hyötyä ja joka on sellaisenaan asiakkaan käyttöön otettavissa.

Ks. myös <https://iri.suomi.fi/terminology/tuha/concept-18205>

Source: CSC.